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BRAINS VS. SCREENS: EXAMINING HOW SMARTPHONES SHAPE ACADEMIC OUTCOMES IN YOUNG LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This study, conducted at Binulho Elementary School, Javier, Leyte investigated the effects of smartphone use on the academic performance of intermediate pupils. Using descriptive and correlational methods, data were gathered from 30 respondents through surveys and statistical analysis.

Smartphones have become a ubiquitous tool in the modern world, successfully replacing desktop computers for several activities due to their portability and computing abilities (Haleem et al., 2022). The purpose of this study was to understand how these devices affect pupils' academic performance. While existing literature has extensively explored this relationship in university settings, there is a recognized research gap concerning the specific impact on elementary school students. This study therefore aimed to filling this gap by focusing on the intermediate level.

Results revealed that smartphone use had a moderate impact across various factors, including parental supervision, socioeconomic status, access to learning resources, study habits, and purpose of use. While smartphones supported learning and organization, they also posed distractions, especially when used for non-academic activities. The average academic performance of the pupils remained high, with a mean grade of 89.13. Correlation analysis showed moderately positive relationships with age and sex, and a moderately negative relationship with grade level, though none were statistically significant. The findings highlight the need for structured interventions to guide responsible smartphone use and support academic success.

Keywords: *smartphone use, academic performance, parental supervision, socioeconomic status, study habits, digital literacy*

INTRODUCTION

Smartphones are the new generation of mobile phones; they have emerged over the last few years and already have conquered the market. Smartphones with their mini keyboards are not just phones, but have computer functions as email, calendar and address book, and office programs for reading and editing (Kohler, 2023). The multimedia phone features such as camera, video, sound recordings or podcasting is advanced and can compete with specialized equipment. Smartphones can be customized with new software, and the variety of these programs is increasing (TECNO, 2020; Nuhel, 2021). The social communication platforms (like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp, etc.), GPS functions and games are especially popular.

The aim of this study is to know how using smartphones affects pupils' academic performance. In these advancements, a smartphone is a device, similar to a computer operating system, having

computing abilities and connectivity options. These were released in 2000, and from that period they became some popular and desirable gadgets for everyone (Haleem et al., 2022). Smartphones have successfully replaced desktop computers for a number of activities because it's a small smart device that everyone can easily keep inside a pocket (Limniou, 2021). It has become an integral part of today's generation in every aspect of life especially for students and youngsters who are the major users or consumers of smartphones (Hossain, 2019).

As defined by Obadofin et al. (2020), performance as the obvious expression or demonstration of sympathetic, ideas, skills and knowledge of a person and planned grade clearly indicate the performance of a student. So, student's academic performance is given more emphasis and keeping in view all the factors adversely or positively impact on their academic performance.

Statement of the Problem

This study investigates the effect of smartphones on the academic performances of intermediate pupils in Binulho Elementary School. Specifically, it examines the potential factors that may influence the bridge between smartphone use and academic performance.

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex,
 - 1.3 Grade level
2. What is the effect of using smartphones commonly experienced by the pupils in terms of the following variables?
 - 2.1 Parental supervision of smartphone use
 - 2.2 Socioeconomic status (SES)
 - 2.3 Access to other learning resources
 - 2.4 Study habits
 - 2.5 Purpose of smartphone use
3. What is the academic performances of pupils using smartphones?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance and using smartphones when grouped according to their demographic profile (age, sex, and grade level)?
5. Based on the results of the study, what interventions programs can be proposed to help address the problem?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive quantitative design to examine how smartphone use affects the academic performance of intermediate pupils. It also explored related indicators and possible solutions for managing smartphone impact, providing a detailed overview of the current academic environment concerning smartphone use. Descriptive research is characterized by its rigor and focus on uncovering information and accurately interpreting findings. It is particularly useful for assessing current conditions, common behaviors, ongoing situations, and observable phenomena (Siedlecki, 2020).

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were 30 students from Binulho Elementary School, selected through **stratified sampling**. These elementary pupils were chosen because they are particularly

affected by smartphone usage, especially in terms of academic performance. The study emphasizes the importance of guiding students to use smartphones efficiently to support and enhance their academic achievement.

Locale of the Study

. The study was conducted in Javier, Leyte, Philippines, specifically at Binulho Elementary School. Javier is a municipality located in the Eastern Visayas region of Leyte. The researchers reside in the municipality, which made Binulho Elementary School a convenient site for data collection and collaboration throughout the study.

Research Instruments and Validation

This current study used a survey questionnaire with two sections: the first collected demographic information (age, gender, grade level, smartphone usage), and the second assessed the effect of smartphone use on academic performance using Likert scale items. The questionnaire was pre-tested for clarity, and the collected data were analyzed through descriptive and correlational statistics.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data were collected at Binulho Elementary School with ethical approval and parental consent. A paper-based questionnaire, pre-tested on a pilot group, was administered to students during class or convenient times. Researchers ensured data accuracy by carefully managing responses and addressing missing or inconsistent data, maintaining data integrity and participant welfare.

Ethical Consideration

This study followed key ethical standards, securing consent from Binulho Elementary School's head committee and informed consent from participants. It ensured transparency about the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits, allowed voluntary withdrawal, maintained confidentiality through data anonymization and secure storage, and presented results in a way that protected participant privacy and prevented harm.

Method of Scoring and Interpretation

1. Respondents Profile Variables
 - 1.1 Sex

	Code
Male	1
Female	2
 - 1.2 Grade Level

Grade 4 below	1
Grade 5	2
Grade 6	3
2. Likert Scale
 - 5 – Strongly Agree
 - 4 – Agree
 - 3 - Neutral

2– Disagree

1– Strongly Disagree

3. Mean Scores Interpretation

Scale	Qualitative Description
4.20 – 5.00	Very High Impact
3.40 – 4.19	High Impact
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate Impact
1.80 – 2.59	Low Impact
1.0 – 1.79	Very Low Impact

4. Curriculum Interpretation Guide on Correlation

Range	Verbal Interpretation
± 1.00	Perfect Correlation
$\pm 0.76 - \pm 0.99$	Very high positive/negative correlation
$\pm 0.51 - \pm 0.75$	High positive/negative correlation
$\pm 0.26 - \pm 0.50$	Moderately small positive/negative correlation
$\pm 0.01 - \pm 0.25$	Very small positive/negative correlation
0.00	No correlation

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistic, frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient to examine relationships between variables. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software was used to process and interpret the data according to the study's objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
10 below	18	60.0
13	8	26.7
12 above	4	13.3

	Total	30	Total	100%
Sex				
Male		11		36.67
Female		19		63.33
	Total	30	Total	100%
Grade level				
4		7		23.3
5		13		43.3
6		10		33.3
	Total	30	Total	100%

Table 1

Percentage Allocation of Respondents Across Demographic Variables

Age. Among the 30 pupils from Binulho Elementary, 60% were aged 10 and below, 26.7% were 11 years old, and 13.3% were 12 or older. This sample mostly includes younger learners, which could affect the impact of smartphone use on their academic performance, especially regarding early cognitive development and learning habits.

Sex. Among the 30 pupils surveyed at Binulho Elementary, 63.33% were girls and 36.67% were boys, indicating a majority of female participants, which may influence patterns of smartphone use and its effects on academic performance.

Grade Level. Of the 30 respondents from Binulho Elementary, 43.3% were in Grade 5, 33.3% in Grade 6, and 23.3% in Grade 4 or below. Most participants were in upper elementary levels, which is important when studying the influence of smartphone use on academic performance, as older pupils often use digital tools more and face greater academic challenges.

Weighted Mean on the Level of Effect of Smartphones in Terms of Parental Supervision

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Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
My parents/guardians limit the amount of time I can use my smartphone for non-school activities on school days.	3.0	Moderate Impact
My parents/guardians check if I am using my smartphone for schoolwork or just for fun.	3.10	Moderate Impact
My parents/guardians help me plan when I can use my smartphone so it doesn't interfere with my studying.	2.97	Moderate Impact
My parents/guardians get involved in how I use my smartphone for learning, like helping me find educational apps.	2.97	Moderate Impact
My parents/guardians talk to me about balancing my smartphone use with my schoolwork and grades.	2.93	Moderate Impact
Overall Weighted Mean	2.99	Moderate Impact

Table 2

Data show that parental supervision moderately influences the smartphone habits of 30 Binulho Elementary pupils, with an overall weighted mean of 2.99. The most emphasized aspect is monitoring whether the smartphone is used for schoolwork or entertainment (mean = 3.10), indicating focus on content checking over time or educational guidance.

**Weighted Mean on the Level of Effect of Smartphones
in Terms of Socioeconomic Status (SES).**

SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (SES)	MEAN	Verbal Interpretation
My family has enough money to buy the things we need.	2.5	Low Impact
I have access to a quiet place at home where I can study without being disturbed.	2.4	Low Impact
My parents/guardians have completed higher levels of education (e.g., college, university).	2.33	Low Impact
My family owns more than one smartphone or similar device.	3.57	High Impact
I have access to a reliable internet connection at home.	3.2	Moderate Impact
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.80	Moderate Impact

Table 3

Table 3 shows that smartphone use among the 30 Binulho Elementary pupils has a moderate impact related to socioeconomic status (overall mean = 2.80). Device ownership (mean = 3.57) and internet access (3.20) had the highest impact, while parental education, study environment, and financial sufficiency showed low impact, indicating that access to technology drives smartphone engagement more than other SES factors.

**Weighted Mean on the Level of Effect of Smartphones by the Pupils
in Terms of Access to Other Learning Resources**

ACCESS TO OTHER LEARNING RESOURCES	MEAN	VI
My smartphone allows me to easily access learning materials provided by my teachers (e.g., notes, assignments).	2.87	Moderate Impact

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I can quickly find information online using my smartphone to help me understand my school lessons better.	3.27	Moderate Impact
My smartphone makes it easier for me to collaborate with classmates on school projects outside of school hours.	3.4	High Impact
I use educational apps on my smartphone to practice and improve my understanding of different subjects.	3.07	Moderate Impact
Having a smartphone helps me stay organized with my schoolwork by allowing me to access schedules and reminders.	2.37	Low Impact
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.00	Moderate Impact

Table 4

Table 4 indicates that smartphone use among the 30 pupils has a moderate impact on access to learning resources (overall mean = 3.00). The highest impact was on peer collaboration for school projects (mean = 3.40). Moderate impact was also seen in accessing online information, educational apps, and teacher materials, while smartphone use for organization and time management showed a low impact.

**Weighted Mean on the Level of Effect of Smartphones
in Terms of Study Habits.**

STUDY HABITS	MEAN	Verbal Interpretation
When I need to study, I usually turn off notifications on my smartphone to avoid distractions.	3.17	Moderate Impact
I often use my smartphone to help me organize my study schedule and tasks.	3.03	Moderate Impact
I find myself checking my smartphone for non-study related things even when I am trying to do my homework.	2.47	Low Impact
I believe using my smartphone to access online study materials (like notes or videos) helps me learn better.	2.87	Moderate Impact
I feel that having my smartphone nearby makes it harder for me to concentrate on studying for long periods.	3.13	Low Impact
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.93	Moderate Impact

Table 5

Table 2.4 indicates that smartphone use among the 30 pupils of Binulho Elementary School has a moderate impact on their study habits, with an overall weighted mean of 2.93. Pupils moderately benefit from using smartphones to organize study schedules (mean = 3.03) and access online learning materials (mean = 2.87), while some demonstrate self-regulation by turning off notifications during study time (mean = 3.17). However, low-impact ratings were observed in behaviors such as checking non-study content during homework (mean = 2.47) and difficulty concentrating with smartphones nearby (mean = 3.13), suggesting that distractions remain a concern.

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**Weighted Mean on the Level of effect of Smartphones
in Terms of Purpose of Smartphone**

PURPOSE OF SMARTPHONE USE	MEAN	VI
I mostly use my smartphone for school-related tasks like research or homework.	3.07	Moderate Impact
I spend more time using my smartphone for entertainment (e.g., games, social media, videos) than for schoolwork.	3.0	Moderate Impact
My smartphone helps me to organize my schoolwork and keep track of deadlines.	3.13	Moderate Impact
I use my smartphone to communicate with classmates about school projects or assignments.	2.77	Moderate Impact
I find that using my smartphone for non-school activities often takes away time I could be using for studying.	3.43	High Impact
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.08	Moderate Impact

Table 6

Based on the data presented in Table 2.5, the overall weighted mean of 3.08 indicates a moderate impact of smartphone use on pupils' academic performance in terms of its purpose. While smartphones are moderately used for school-related tasks such as research (mean = 3.07), organizing schoolwork (mean = 3.13), and communicating with classmates (mean = 2.77), the highest mean score of 3.43 reflects a high impact of non-academic usage, suggesting that entertainment and other non-school activities significantly reduce study time.

Grades Obtained from the 30 Respondents.

No. of Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation
30	89.13	2.81

Table 7

In the study conducted at Binulho Elementary School on the effect of smartphone use on academic performance, the 30 pupil respondents achieved an average grade of 89.13, with a standard deviation of 2.81. This indicates a generally high level of academic performance among the participants, with relatively low variability in their grades, suggesting consistent achievement across the group.

Correlation Between the Effect of Using Smartphones on the Academic Performance when Grouped According to Their Demographic Profile

PROFILE CHARACTERISTICS	PEARSON CORRELATION	SIG.	ADJECTIVAL INTERPRETATION

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Age	.300	.107	Moderately Positive Correlation
Sex	.300	.108	Moderately Positive Correlation
Grade Level	-.263	.160	Moderately Negative Correlation

In the study conducted at Binulho Elementary School on the effect of smartphone use on academic performance, correlation analysis revealed moderately positive relationships between smartphone use and academic performance when grouped by age ($r = .300$, $p = .107$) and sex ($r = .300$, $p = .108$), suggesting that older pupils and female pupils may experience slightly more favorable academic outcomes associated with smartphone use. Conversely, a moderately negative correlation was observed with grade level ($r = -.263$, $p = .160$), indicating that as pupils progress to higher grades, the academic impact of smartphone use may decline.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study conducted at Binulho Elementary School examined the effects of smartphone use on the academic performance of elementary pupils. It found that smartphones offer moderate benefits by enhancing access to learning resources, aiding organization of schoolwork, and supporting study habits, but can also be distracting when used for non-academic purposes. Parental supervision showed a moderate positive influence, while socioeconomic factors such as internet access and device availability impacted learning experiences. Despite these mixed effects, the overall academic performance of pupils remained high, with an average grade of 89.13.

To optimize benefits and address challenges, the study recommends collaboration between schools and parents on structured digital literacy programs that promote responsible smartphone use. This includes regular workshops, clear school policies, and active parental involvement to help pupils balance screen time with academic priorities. Additionally, improving access to educational apps, providing quiet study environments, and ensuring reliable internet—especially for lower-income pupils—can support academic growth. Teachers should also integrate smartphones effectively into lessons, and counselors should guide students in managing their digital habits to improve learning outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Haleem, A., Javaid, M., Qadri, M. A., & Suman, R. (2022). *Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review*. *Sustainable Operations and Computers*, 3(1), 275–285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/>
- Kohler, T. (2023, May 28). *How Screen-Reader Users Type on and Control Mobile Devices*. Nielsen Norman Group. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/>
- Limniou, M. (2021). *The Effect of Digital Device Usage on Student Academic Performance: A Case Study*. *Education Sciences*, 11(3), 121. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11030121>
- Nuhel, A. K. (2021, October). *Evolution of Smartphone*. ResearchGate. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>

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Obadofin, P. B., Onyeka, E. B., Onukwube, O., & Nchedochukwu, E. (2020). *Impacts Of Smartphone Addiction on Academic Performance of Students in Senior Secondary Schools In Lagos State*.
<https://www.ijramr.com/sites/default/files/issues-pdf/3202.pdf>

Siedlecki, S. (2020). *Understanding Descriptive Research Designs and Methods* | Request PDF. ResearchGate; www.researchgate.net.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338300876_Understanding_Descriptive_Research_Designs_and_Methods

TECNO. (2020, March 5). *Smartphone innovation in the third decade of the 21st century*. MIT Technology Review. <https://www.technologyreview.com>

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